

RESEARCH ARTICLE

 OPEN ACCESS

Received: 03-02-2023

Accepted: 11-03-2023

Published: 12-04-2023

Citation: Tharanatha A, Shashidhar R, Bharath S, Nagesh P (2023) The Green Behaviour Role in Relationship Amid Green Human Resource Management and Employer Branding in Green Hospitals. Indian Journal of Science and Technology 16(14): 1062-1068. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v16i14.247>

* **Corresponding author.**pnagesh1973@rediffmail.com**Funding:** None**Competing Interests:** None

Copyright: © 2023 Tharanatha et al. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment ([iSee](https://www.isee.org/))

ISSN

Print: 0974-6846

Electronic: 0974-5645

The Green Behaviour Role in Relationship Amid Green Human Resource Management and Employer Branding in Green Hospitals

Ananya Tharanatha¹, R Shashidhar², Sindu Bharath^{3,4}, P Nagesh^{4*}

1 Research Scholar, Institute of Management Studies, Davanagere University, Davanagere, India

2 Professor, Institute of Management Studies, Davanagere University, Davanagere, India

3 Associate Professor, Institute of Management Studies, Davanagere University, Davanagere, India

4 JSS Centre for Management Studies, JSS Science and Technology University, Mysuru, 570 006

Abstract

Objectives: The purpose of this paper is to examine the role of Green Behaviour (GB) in relationship amid Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) and Employer Branding (EB) in Selected Green Hospitals. **Methods:** This empirical research examines dual directions of considered variables The GHRM is studied by adopting the 24-item scale with 6 factors (scale reliability varies from 0.804 to 0.814). GB is measured by adopting 6 item scale with 2 factors (reliability ranges from 0.821 to 0.834). To examine perceived EB, 23 item scale with 6 factors (reliability varies from 0.813 to 0.817) were applied. The responses were collected using convenience sampling through the e-mail survey and 384 valid responses (Health Care Professionals in Selected Green Hospitals) were considered. Data Analysis is carried out in dual stages viz., scale validation for all considered variables and Sobel test is carried out to examine the mediating role of GB amid GHRM and EB. **Findings:** The results of the analysis explored that mediation investigation were satisfied and reinforced, it also noted that after removal of mediating variables (GB), the β weight of the GB is reduced from 0.899 to 0.706 which is significant. Hence, GB acts as a partial mediator in relationship amid GB and EB which is confirmed by sobel test. **Novelty:** The examination of the GB practices as a mediating role amid GHRM and EB in a single study is a uniqueness of this research.

Keywords: Green Human Resource Management; Green Behaviour; Employer Branding; Health Care sector; Sobel Test

1 Introduction

The Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) includes green recruitment-selection, learning and development, performance monitoring and compensation systems which leads to green workplace and contributes to sustainable business

organization. The pollution and global-warming have created growing pressure to implement GHRM practices to create environmental eco system. GHRM is a HRM-Centric approach⁽¹⁾ and effective GHRM enhances the employee's green skills and results in increased organizational commitment⁽²⁾, also leads gain competitive advantage⁽³⁾.

In addition, the organization efforts towards implementing green practices shall be complimented by individual contribution towards accomplishment of green objectives, which is an important green business attribute. The employees' green behaviour covers both in-role and extra-role behaviours which contributes to sustainable goals⁽⁴⁾.

Employer Branding helps in retaining current and attracting potential employees to understand the work value preferences as it varies across time and culture. Integration of green practices and behaviour results in Employer Branding (EB). The right blend of EB Dimensions (EBD) is vital to keep employees glued to organization.

GHRM practices is limited to few HR functions such as hiring, training and development, geographical region and emerging countries, thus requiring extension of the practices to other domain of HR functions such as performance management system, compensation system. These days, GHRM practices and their impact is relatively higher in health care sector and hospitals are striving to implement green workplace towards creating sustainable green hospitals so as to build the green branding. Going beyond the previous research this study seeks to throw light on Green Behaviour (GB), GHRM and EB.

While the literature on GHRM practices and their impact on health care sector is scarce. As GHRM impacts the Employee Green Behaviour there is a need to examine the interaction of each other more specifically in Green Hospitals⁽⁵⁾. The literatures on GHRM impact on sustainable performance is also limited⁽⁶⁾ and therefore there is a need to study and validate the influence of GB between GHRM and EB⁽⁷⁾. A strong GHRM system is essential to deliver the value propositions to Green Attitude, Eco-Innovation, Sustainable Environmental Strategy, Green Procurement and supply chain, Green Managerial Awareness and Green Technology of product and services. GHRM practices are still emerging in developing countries which require attention from decision-makers in the healthcare sector. Despite green human resource management receiving significant interest from scholars, studies related to green practices remain limited. Thus, current research attempts to examine the role of GB in relationship amid GHRM and EB in Selected Green Hospitals.

2 Methodology

The present quantitative research examines the dual directions of considered variables. First, the direct effect of GB on GHRM is examined. Further, the direct effect of GB on EB is studied. Further, mediating effect of GB amid GHRM and EB is established. The structure questionnaire was designed with four sections, first section on the demographic information, second on GHRM, third on GB and fourth on EB. The instrument (Likert-Scale) was validated with model fitness indexes using AMOS. The GHRM is studied by adopting the 24 item scale with 6 factors (scale reliability varies from 0.804 to 0.814). GB is measured by adopting 6 item scale with 2 factors (reliability ranges from 0.821 to 0.834). To examine perceived EB, 23 item scale with 6 factors (reliability varies from 0.813 to 0.817) was applied. The CR of the scale were 0.814, 0.818 and 0.839 respectively, which are acceptable. The responses were collected using convenience sampling method through the e-mail survey and 384 valid responses (Health Care Professionals in Selected Green Hospitals) were considered. The data were collected during August-November 2022. The pilot testing is done with 65 respondents to remove indistinctness. Convenience sampling was adopted to choose the respondents.

3 Results and Discussion

Data Analysis is carried out in three stages viz., scale validation is done for 3 variables considered in present research (GHRM, GB and EB). Further, mediating role of GB amid GHRM and EB is established, the results are discussed in below section.

3.1 Green Human Resource Management(GHRM)

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test value is 0.874, which indicates the sample adequacy. The EFA is adopted using Principal Component Analysis (Vari-max-rotation method) which explains 67.45% of total variance. CFA validated the extracted factors using AMOS software. Based on the Eigenvalue (unity), 24 items and 6 factors were confirmed (Figure 1). They were grouped considering the relevance of items such as GHR Planning, Recruitment-Selection, Performance Management Indicators, Learning and Development, Reward and Discipline management features. The model fit indices were noted as CMIN/DF ratio = 2.370, GFI = .900, AGFI = .956, IFI=.929, TLI,=.914 and RMSEA=.063. Fit indices signifies good measurement model⁽⁸⁾. Thus, the proposed measurement model is adequate to measure the GHRM.

Fig 1. CFA- GHRM

Table 1. FA- Fit-Indices

Fit-Indices	Values	Acceptable criteria
CMIN/DF Ratio	2.370	Less than 4
GFI,	0.900	
AGFI,	0.956	
CFI,	0.928	More than 0.9
IFI	0.929	
TLI,	0.914	
RMSEA	0.063	Less than 0.08

3.2 Green Behaviour (GB)

The KMO test value is 0.847, indicating sample adequacy. The EFA explains 67.64% of total variance. CFA validated the extracted 2 factors along with 6 items (Figure 2), which were grouped and labelled based on relevance of items such as; Green - In-Role and Green- Extra role Behaviours. Confirmed model fit indices were noted as CMIN/DF ratio = 2.129, GFI, = .892, AGFI, = .897, IFI,=.929, TLL,=.914 and RMSEA.,=.063. Fit indices signifies that the proposed measurement model is adequate to measure the Green Behaviour (GB).

3.3 Employer Branding (EB)

The KMO test value is 0.847, indicating sample adequacy. The EFA explains 69.14% of total variance. CFA validated the extracted 6 factors along with 24 items using AMOS software (Figure 2), which were grouped and labelled as; Empathy, Benchmarking, Job-Quality, Communication, Information sharing also promotional features.

Fig 2. CFA- GB

Table 2. CFA- Fit-Indices

Model fit-Indices	Value	Acceptable criteria
CMIN/DF Ratio	2.129	Less than 4
GFI,	.892	
AGFI,	.897	
CFI,	.928	More than 0.9
IFI,	.929	
TLI,	.914	
RMSEA,	.063	Less than 0.08

The confirmed model fit indices were noted as CMIN/DF ratio = 2.647, GFI, = .896, AGFI, = .901, IFI,=.894, TLI,=.912 and RMSEA,= .056. As fit indices were nearer to unity, proposed measurement model is adequate to measure EB⁽⁸⁾.

Table 3. FA- Fit-Indices

Model fit-Indices	Values	Acceptable criteria
CMIN/DF,	2.647	Less than 4
GFI,	0.896	
AGF,	0.901	
CFI,	0.914	More than 0.9
IFI,	0.894	
TLI,	0.912	
RMSEA,	0.056	Less than 0.08

Fig 3. CFA- EB

3.4 Mediation analysis

The present study was to examine proposed hypothesis; GHRM has direct impact on EB (H₁), GB has direct impact on EB (H₂), GHRM has direct impact on GB (H₃) and GB has a direct mediating effect between GHRM and EB (H₄). The GB is significant and directly related with respect to EB ($\beta = .899, p < .001$), GB is directly related with EB ($\beta = .749, p < .001$) and GB is noteworthy and directly related to GHRM ($\beta = .740, p < .001$).

Fig 4. Mediating Role of GB amid GHRM and EB associated with Digital Buying

The multiple regression analysis indicates that; the first 3 steps of the mediation investigation were satisfied-reinforced. It is also explored that after removal of mediating variable (GB), β weight of the GB is reduced from 0.899 to 0.706. Hence, GB act as a partial mediator in relationship amid GHRM and EB.

In addition, Sobel test is steered to confirm the significance of the mediation effect of GB, test statistic ($z = 3.01, p < .001$) reveals that there exists no proof to reject the pre-stated Null hypothesis. Thus, GB mediates the relationship amid GHRM and EB. Thus, results may be summarized as; GHRM has a positive impact on EB (H₁), GB has a direct impact on EB (H₂), GHRM has a direct impact on GB (H₃) and GB has a direct mediating role amid GHRM and EB (H₄). The results of the multiple regression analysis explored that first 3 steps of the mediation investigation were satisfied and reinforced, it also explored that

Table 4. Mediating Analysis Results: Role of CRM amid DBB and RF

Mediation Steps	Unstandardized β	SE	Standardized β	t	Significance Level
Step A	0.894	0.068	0.899	10.869	0.000
Step B	0.861	0.088	0.749	7.043	0.000
Step C	0.699	0.067	0.740	7.013	0.000
Step D	0.801	0.071	0.706	9.001	0.000
Sobel Test: Findings					
Type of Mediation.	Z-Score	Effects			Significance Level
		Direct	Indirect	Total	
Partial	3.01	.601	.256	.857	0.000

* Controlled variable (GHRM), predicted variable (EB), Mediating variable (GB)

after removal of mediating variables (GB), the β weight of the GB is reduced from 0.899 to 0.706 which is significant. Hence, GB acts as a partial mediator in relationship amid GB and EB.

The GB acts as a partial mediator amid GHRM and EB. Thus, in a strategic context, health care sectors need to design and implement the effective GB process to align the GHRM considering EB also GB which has a positive impact on EB significantly, present study findings are in line with findings of⁽⁹⁾. The GHRM affects GB through the full mediation of environmental knowledge. The present study explored that the status and challenges of GHRM practices are also in line with⁽¹⁰⁾ who also explored the status and challenges of GHRM practices in India with multimethod approach. Further, pro-environmental behaviour in the organizations is encouraged in Green Hospitals. Similar to the outcome of the present study, GHRM practices significantly predicts the employee green behaviours⁽¹¹⁾. It is also noted that GHRM assists voluntary employee green behaviours in Indian Automobile Industry. The green recruiting and selection facility, organizational culture, purchasing, strategy, regulatory forces the management commitment towards greening the workforce and work place⁽¹²⁾. Similar to the outcome of the present study, there is a significant relationship between environmental performance (EP) and business performance (BP). The mediation analysis of present study emphasizes the role of GB on GHRM, which is also noted by⁽¹³⁾, green HRM positively influences environmental performance and employees job satisfaction.

The outcome of present study is supported by⁽⁷⁾ which indicate the significant influence of GHRM on GB and Green Knowledge Sharing.⁽¹⁴⁾ shed light from the Spanish approach that an effective implementation of green-growth strategies contributes to environmental strategic goals.⁽¹⁵⁾ demonstrates the relationship between GHRM and EB and provides a convincing reason for firms to use GHRM practices in crafting eco-friendly employer branding initiatives.⁽¹⁶⁾ mentions that green awareness of the employee enables an organization to achieve its sustainability and strategic green goals. Also, green employer branding generally develops the green reputation⁽¹⁷⁾. Hospital management are expected to implement GHRM that may produce high level of environmental performance and service quality^(18,19) evaluates GHRM practices with Green Performance (GP) by empirically supporting the mediation and moderation model.

⁽²⁰⁾ echoes that GHRM aligns the workers' attitude and behaviour regarding environmental protection. GHRM has a link between human resource practices to positive work-related behaviour and outcomes⁽²¹⁾. Further,⁽²²⁾ confirmed the mediating role of Climate Practices (CP) in the relationship between GHRM and GB in workplace.

4 Conclusion

The multiple regression analysis indicates that; the first 3 steps of the mediation investigation were satisfied-reinforced. It also explored that after removal of mediating variables, β weight of the GB is reduced from 0.899 to 0.706. GHRM has a positive impact on EB (H1), GB has a direct impact on EB (H2), GHRM has a positive impact on GB (H3) and GB has a direct mediating effect between GHRM and EB (H4). The GB is positively related with EB ($\beta = .899, p < .001$), GB is directly associated with EB ($\beta = .749, p < .001$) and GB is noteworthy and directly related to GHRM ($\beta = .740, p < .001$). Hence, GB act as a partial mediator in relationship amid GHRM and EB. In addition, Sobel test is confirming the significance of the mediation effect of GB, test statistic ($z = 3.01, p < .001$). Besides, the mediating effects of GB amid EB and GHRM, GB play vital role in building effective green workforce.

The study findings indicate that GB process should embrace effective GHRM driven by green organizations. It is decisive to hold GB effective to stimulate GHRM towards implementing EB intension. The present study shows that GB practices as a mediating role amid GHRM and EB in a single study which is uniqueness of this research. The research outcome helps to develop HR policies for promoting environment management initiatives to bridge the gap between professional implementation

of green HRM. The green Learning- development, performance and participations were vital to develop the EB of the firm. A strong GHRM system essential to deliver the value propositions to Green Attitude, Eco-Innovation, Sustainable Environmental Strategy, Green Procurement and supply chain, Green Managerial Awareness and Green Technology of product and services. Health care sector HR professionals need to work out right permutation and combination of these three factors to achieve right mix of green workplace also these variabilities to design Integrated GHRM Process. Thus, the study has important theoretical and managerial implications for further research in GB, EB and GHRM.

This study has certain limitations which may be explored by future researchers. First, data were obtained from employees (Health Care Professionals) of health care sector in Bangalore city, India which may also affect the accuracy of the universal judgment at the national level. Second, current study adopted purely quantitative approach. Therefore, considering these limitations into account, we call future researchers to explore on qualitative research.

References

- Ghouri AM, Mani V, Khan MR, Khan NR, Srivastava AP. Enhancing business performance through green human resource management practices: an empirical evidence from Malaysian manufacturing industry. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*. 2020;69(8):1585–1607. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPPM-11-2019-0520>.
- Bahuguna PC, Srivastava R, Tiwari S. Two-decade journey of green human resource management research: a bibliometric analysis. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*. 2023;30(2):585–602. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-10-2021-0619>.
- Shoab M, Abbas Z, Yousof M, Zámečník R, Ahmed J, Saqib S. The role of GHRM practices towards organizational commitment: A mediation analysis of green human capital. *Cogent Business & Management*. 2021;8(1):1870798. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2020.1870798>.
- Muisyo PK, Qin S. Enhancing the FIRM'S green performance through green HRM: The moderating role of green innovation culture. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 2021;289:125720. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.125720>.
- Anwar N, Mahmood NHN, Yusliza MY, Ramayah T, Faezah JN, Khalid W. Green Human Resource Management for organisational citizenship behaviour towards the environment and environmental performance on a university campus. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 2020;256:120401–120401. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.120401>.
- Yong JY, Yusliza MY, Fawehinmi OO. Green human resource management: A systematic literature review from. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*. 2007;27(7):2005–2027. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-12-2018-0438>.
- Zaid A, Jaaron A. The Impact of Green Human Resource Management Practices with Sustainable and Operational Performance: A Conceptual Model. In: *Innovation of Businesses, and Digitalization during Covid-19 Pandemic*. Springer International Publishing, 2023;p. 583–610. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-08090-6_37.
- Rubel MRB, Kee DMH, Rimi NN. The influence of green HRM practices on green service behaviors: the mediating effect of green knowledge sharing. *Employee Relations: The International Journal*. 2021;43(5):996–1015. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/ER-04-2020-0163>.
- Nanjundeswaraswamy TS, Bharath S, Nagesh P. Employer branding: design and development of a scale. *Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences*. 2022. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEAS-01-2022-0012>.
- Fawehinmi O, Yusliza MY, Mohamad Z, Faezah N, Muhammad J, Z. Assessing the green behaviour of academics: The role of green human resource management and environmental knowledge. *International Journal of Manpower*. 2020;41(7). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJM-07-2019-0347>.
- Chaudhary R. Green human resource management in Indian automobile industry. *Journal of Global Responsibility*. 2019;10(2):161–175. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JGR-12-2018-0084>.
- Moktadir MA, Dwivedi A, Ali SM, Paul SK, Kabir G, Madaan J. Antecedents for greening the workforce: implications for green human resource management. *International Journal of Manpower*. 2019;41(7):1135–1153. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJM-07-2019-0354>.
- Shafaei A, Nejati M, Yusoff M, Y. Green human resource management: A two-study investigation of antecedents and outcomes. *International Journal of Manpower*. 2020;41(7). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJM-08-2019-0406>.
- Aboramadan M. The effect of green HRM on employee green behaviors in higher education: the mediating mechanism of green work engagement. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*. 2022;30(1):7–23. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOA-05-2020-2190>.
- Labella-Fernández A. Archetypes of green-growth strategies and the role of green human resource management in their implementation. 2021. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-95726-5_113.
- Muisyo PK, Qin S, Julius MM, Ho TH, Ho TH. Green HRM and employer branding: the role of collective affective commitment to environmental management change and environmental reputation. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*. 2022;30(8):1897–1914. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2021.1988621>.
- Jamal T, Zahid M, Martins JM, Mata MN, Rahman HU, Mata PN. Perceived Green Human Resource Management Practices and Corporate Sustainability: Multigroup Analysis and Major Industries Perspectives. *Sustainability*. 2021;13(6):3045. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13063045>.
- Green H. A New Paradigm for Health Care Sustainability. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*;27(10):42–57. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.9790/0837-2710055257>.
- Mousa SK, Othman M. The impact of green human resource management practices on sustainable performance in healthcare organisations: A conceptual framework. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 2020;243:118595. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.118595>.
- Huo X, Azhar A, Rehman N, Majeed N. The Role of Green Human Resource Management Practices in Driving Green Performance in the Context of Manufacturing SMEs. *Sustainability*. 2022;14(24):16776. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142416776>.
- Ribeiro N, Gomes DR, Ortega E, Gomes GP, Semedo AS. The Impact of Green HRM on Employees' Eco-Friendly Behavior: The Mediator Role of Organizational Identification. *Sustainability*. 2022;14(5):2897. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14052897>.
- Ercantan O, Eyupoglu S. How Do Green Human Resource Management Practices Encourage Employees to Engage in Green Behavior? Perceptions of University Students as Prospective Employees. *Sustainability*. 2022;14(3):1718. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14031718>.